

SAEGE

Data Management Plan (DMP)

D1.2

Document Information

Title	D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP)
Authors	Lisa Tambornino (EUREC Office gUG), Toby Wardman (EUREC Office gUG)
Project name	Support for the activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies
Project acronym	SAEGE
Project number	101256865
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Last update	29 April 2026

Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme. The views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data governance, lifecycle, and stewardship approach of the SAEGE project. The project supports the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) in delivering independent ethics advice to inform European Union policymaking.

The DMP outlines procedures for data generation, processing, storage, sharing, preservation, and security in compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements, the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and recognised standards of research integrity. It also addresses the responsible use of AI tools in analytical and horizon scanning activities.

As a single-beneficiary action, all data governance, ownership, and responsibility rest with the single beneficiary EUREC Office gUG.

Contents

Document Information	2
Acknowledgement and Disclaimer	2
Abstract	2
Abbreviations	4
Data Summary.....	4
WP1 – Coordination	4
WP2 – Developing evidence-based ethics advice	5
WP3 – Development and coordination of ethics advice network	6
WP4 – Horizon scanning for emerging ethical issues	6
WP5 – Communication and policy engagement	7
FAIR Data	8
Findable	8
Accessible	8
Interoperable	8
Reusable	8
Allocation of Resources	9
Data Security.....	9
Ethical Aspects.....	9
Other Issues	10

Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
EGE	European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
EGEAN	EGE Et Alia Advisory Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SAEGE	Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies
WP	Work Package

Data Summary

According to its Description of Action, the SAEGE project does not intend to collect data beyond what is necessary for the organization of meetings and expert consultations. This raises minimal issues related to personal data, which are professionally addressed by the staff involved in each type of activity. The SAEGE project generates qualitative, analytical, and administrative data to support the ethical advisory work of the European Group on Ethics in Science and new Technologies (EGE). Data generation and use are structured by Work Package (WP), reflecting the operational organisation of the project.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated whenever relevant changes occur during the project. It will be reviewed regularly and updated by EUREC Office gUG when necessary.

WP1 – Coordination

WP1 generates administrative and governance-related data necessary for the effective implementation, monitoring, and reporting of the project. This includes, but is not limited to, meeting minutes, internal and external reporting documentation, quality assurance procedures, ethical compliance records, and iterative updates to the DMP.

The data produced under WP1 is primarily organisational and procedural in nature and is used to ensure transparency, accountability, and compliance with Horizon Europe requirements.

Limited non-sensitive personal data may be processed in the context of coordination activities. This may include names, institutional affiliations, roles, and contact details of project staff, seconded experts, and external contributors. Such data is processed solely for legitimate project purposes, including coordination, communication, reporting, and audit requirements, and is not intended for public dissemination.

All data generated within WP1 is stored securely on the EUREC Office gUG SharePoint environment and on institutional devices managed by EUREC. Access to this data is strictly restricted to authorised personnel on a need-to-know basis. Appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure data integrity, confidentiality, and protection against unauthorised access, in line with GDPR and institutional data security policies.

WP2 – Developing evidence-based ethics advice

WP2 generates the project's core analytical and research data underpinning the development of evidence-based ethics advice for the EGE. This includes data derived from literature reviews, policy analysis, and expert consultations, such as interviews, surveys, workshops, and working group activities.

Where empirical data collection involving human participants is undertaken, all activities are conducted in accordance with established ethical standards. This includes the use of informed consent procedures, the provision of clear participant information, and the prior acquisition of ethics approvals where required. Participation is voluntary, and appropriate safeguards are implemented to protect participants' rights and confidentiality.

In addition to conventional research data, WP2 also generates AI-assisted analytical materials. These may include summaries, structured outputs, prompt logs, validation records, and methodological documentation supporting the use of AI tools in evidence synthesis and ethical analysis. All AI-assisted outputs are subject to systematic human oversight, validation, and quality control to ensure reliability, transparency, and the mitigation of potential bias.

A dedicated activity within WP2 (Task 2.5) focuses on the development of procedures and quality controls for the use of AI in ethics advisory work. This task involves targeted literature reviews, expert consultations, and stakeholder workshops, as well as the piloting of AI tools within the project. The resulting outputs include documented standards, ethical safeguards, and guidance for the responsible integration of AI across project workflows, including evidence-gathering and foresight activities.

Derived analytical outputs, such as reports and synthesis documents, are made publicly available in line with Open Science principles and deposited in Zenodo where appropriate. By contrast, raw data from consultations that may contain personal information is processed in anonymised or aggregated form and is not made publicly accessible.

All data generated under WP2 is securely stored on the EUREC Office gUG Teams SharePoint environment and on institutional systems managed by EUREC. Access is restricted to authorised project personnel, and appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place to ensure data protection, integrity, and compliance with GDPR.

WP3 – Development and coordination of ethics advice network

WP3 generates and manages structured stakeholder data in support of the establishment and operation of the EGE Et Alia Advisory Network (EGEAN). This includes data related to the identification, mapping, engagement, and ongoing coordination of stakeholders within the European and international ethics advisory community, as well as relevant actors affected by emerging ethical challenges in science and technology.

Data generated under this WP includes stakeholder mapping datasets (e.g. sociograms, proximity charts), expert profiles, institutional affiliations, areas of expertise, and records of participation in network activities such as workshops, consultations, and collaborative exercises. These datasets are used to support targeted engagement, evidence-gathering activities under WP2, and the functioning of the network as a resource for the EGE.

Limited personal data is processed in this context, including names, professional roles, institutional affiliations, contact details, and areas of expertise of network members and collaborators. This data is collected and maintained solely for the purposes of network coordination, stakeholder engagement, and facilitating contributions to the project's advisory activities. Processing is carried out in accordance with GDPR principles, including data minimisation, purpose limitation, and restricted access.

WP3 also generates operational data linked to network activities, including records of participation in events, contributions to consultations, and inputs to the "Red Button" early alert mechanism for signalling emerging ethical issues. Where stakeholder input is incorporated into analytical outputs, it is anonymised or aggregated unless explicit consent for attribution has been obtained.

Collaboration activities with science advice institutions at EU level (e.g. through memoranda of understanding or shared procedures) may generate additional organisational and communication data. These data are managed in line with the same principles of confidentiality, security, and responsible use.

All data generated under WP3 is securely stored on the EUREC Office gUG Teams SharePoint environment and on institutional systems managed by EUREC. Access is restricted to authorised personnel involved in stakeholder coordination and project implementation. Appropriate technical and organisational safeguards are in place to ensure the protection, integrity, and confidentiality of the data.

WP4 – Horizon scanning for emerging ethical issues

WP4 generates analytical and foresight-oriented data through the development and operation of an early alert toolbox to identify emerging ethical issues in science and technology. The work relies primarily on the collection and analysis of non-personal data from publicly available digital sources, including scientific publications, policy documents, news media, and online platforms.

Data collection may involve the use of APIs, licensed datasets, RSS feeds, and, where appropriate, web scraping techniques. All data is obtained exclusively from lawfully accessible sources and processed in compliance with GDPR and relevant platform Terms of Service.

The analytical outputs of WP4 include structured datasets of identified signals, trend classifications, and supporting metadata, which form the basis for horizon scanning briefs and further ethical analysis. Data processing may involve the use of computational and AI-supported tools. The development, evaluation, and governance of such tools, including quality assurance procedures and bias mitigation, are addressed in detail under Task 2.5 (WP2).

WP4 also generates qualitative input through expert validation processes and via the “Red Button” early warning mechanism. Where such contributions involve personal data, they are processed in accordance with GDPR and incorporated into outputs in anonymised or aggregated form, unless explicit consent for attribution has been obtained.

All outputs include appropriate documentation of data sources, methodologies, and limitations to ensure transparency. Data generated under WP4 is securely stored on the EUREC Office gUG Teams SharePoint environment and on institutional systems managed by EUREC. Access is restricted to authorised personnel, and appropriate technical and organisational safeguards are in place to ensure data protection and integrity.

WP5 – Communication and policy engagement

WP5 generates data related to the communication, dissemination, and engagement activities of the project. This includes content for publications, the project website, social media outputs, newsletters, multimedia materials (e.g. video and audio), and records related to media engagement and policy outreach.

In addition, WP5 generates operational data associated with events, including participant registration information, attendance records, feedback data, and evaluation metrics. Where relevant, this may include limited non-sensitive personal data such as names, affiliations, and contact details of participants, speakers, and stakeholders. Such data is collected solely for the purpose of organising and evaluating events and is processed in accordance with GDPR principles, including data minimisation and purpose limitation.

The project website serves as a central hub for public information and provides access to project outputs, including materials deposited in Zenodo. Website-related data may include basic usage analytics (e.g. aggregated visitor statistics) to monitor reach and engagement. Any collection and processing of personal data via the website (e.g. through contact forms, newsletter subscriptions, or event registrations) will be conducted in full compliance with GDPR. This includes the provision of clear privacy notices, the use of consent-based mechanisms where required, and the implementation of appropriate safeguards to protect user data. No tracking or profiling beyond standard, proportionate analytics will be conducted.

WP5 also generates data related to media relations and stakeholder engagement activities, including records of interactions with journalists, contributions to public communication outputs, and dissemination tracking (e.g. downloads, reach, and uptake metrics). These data are primarily aggregated and used for monitoring impact and reporting purposes.

All public outputs produced under WP5 are made openly available in line with Open Science principles and are deposited in Zenodo where appropriate. Personal data is not included in publicly accessible materials unless explicit consent for disclosure has been obtained.

All data generated under WP5 is securely stored on the EUREC Office gUG Teams SharePoint environment and on institutional systems managed by EUREC. Access is restricted to authorised personnel, and appropriate technical and organisational safeguards are in place to ensure data protection, integrity, and compliance with applicable legal and ethical standards.

FAIR Data

The SAEGE project applies the FAIR principles to all eligible research outputs in line with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements.

Findable

All openly shareable research outputs and dissemination materials are deposited in the Zenodo repository and assigned persistent identifiers (DOIs). Metadata includes funding information, project acronym, authorship, keywords, and versioning, following OpenAIRE recommendations. The project website provides an additional discovery and access layer.

Accessible

Non-sensitive data and publications are made openly accessible via Zenodo and the project website. Access restrictions apply only where required by GDPR, confidentiality, or ethical considerations, in line with the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

Interoperable

Data is stored in widely accepted standard formats (e.g. PDF/A, CSV, XLSX) to ensure interoperability and long-term accessibility. Metadata practices are applied consistently. AI-assisted analytical workflows are documented to support transparency and interpretability.

Reusable

Openly shared data is accompanied by appropriate documentation describing methodologies, assumptions, and limitations. Clear licensing information is provided, and open licences such as

Creative Commons are applied where appropriate. Personal or sensitive data is anonymised or excluded prior to dissemination.

Allocation of Resources

Data management activities are integrated into the overall project work plan and are coordinated under WP1. These activities include data curation, anonymisation, documentation, metadata creation, and deposition of outputs in open repositories.

The necessary resources are primarily covered through project personnel and existing institutional infrastructure. Secure internal storage is provided via EUREC Office systems, while Zenodo is used for the long-term preservation and open access dissemination of eligible outputs.

No additional significant costs are foreseen beyond standard project operational resources.

Data Security

A unified technical and organisational security framework is applied across all data processing activities within the project. All data is stored on secure, access-controlled institutional systems, primarily within the EUREC Office gUG Teams SharePoint environment, with role-based access and authorisation.

Personal and other sensitive data is logically separated from analytical datasets to minimise risk and ensure appropriate protection. Technical safeguards include secure servers, encryption where appropriate, strong authentication procedures, regular backups, and secure remote access in line with institutional cybersecurity policies.

Organisational measures include structured file management, version control, and audit trails to ensure traceability and accountability. Physical documents, where applicable, are stored securely with restricted access.

Ethical Aspects

The project processes only limited, non-sensitive personal data, such as names, professional affiliations, contact details, and participation records. No special categories of personal data, as defined under Article 9 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), are collected.

No research activities involving vulnerable populations are currently foreseen. Project activities focus on ethical analysis, evidence synthesis, professional stakeholder engagement, and horizon scanning based on publicly available or lawfully licensed sources.

All personal data processing complies with the GDPR and is guided by the principles of lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, and confidentiality. Participants are provided with clear information about data processing activities, and informed consent is obtained where applicable.

At the time of drafting this DMP, the project does not foresee research activities requiring formal ethics approval for sensitive or high-risk data processing. However, should the scope of activities evolve (e.g. involving interviews, surveys, or engagement with vulnerable groups), the beneficiary commits to obtaining prior approval from the relevant institutional ethics committee before such activities commence. No such data collection will take place without appropriate ethical clearance and full compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements.

All ethics approvals obtained, where applicable, will be documented and stored centrally under project coordination to ensure traceability, accountability, and audit readiness.

AI tools used within the project are governed by principles of transparency, fairness, accountability, and human oversight. AI is used exclusively to support analytical processes and does not replace expert judgement. Its use is further governed by dedicated procedures and quality controls developed under Task 2.5.

Other Issues

No additional data management issues have been identified at this stage. This DMP is a living document and will be reviewed and updated as necessary throughout the project duration to reflect methodological, technical, legal, or ethical developments.